

Fig. 1. Result of MPI Communication Microbenchmark with message size equal to, 0.1x size of, and 3.0x size of what our application uses during communication in our paper.

(Reviewer:4) Asynchronous-Progression and OpenMPI

We were surprised that we did not observe the asynchronous progression when we used OpenMPI in our cluster although the Infiniband that we were using has support for it. We thought that it was to be expected as presented by other works in this area¹. Currently, we are renewing our allocation on IBM POWER9 Cluster and thus we run the microbenchmark on our Intel clusters. We compare OpenMPI and Intel MPI in Intel-based cluster with Infiniband. The result of OpenMPI should be representative if we run the microbenchmark on IBM POWER9 Cluster.

It is explicitly stated that Intel MPI support asynchronous progression², whereas we do not see the same thing for OpenMPI. This is also consistent with our observations: perfect overlap between computation and communication for Intel MPI, but not for OpenMPI. We also tried to forcefully move the messages by using MPI_Test and MPI_Probe, but they did not help.

For running the microbenchmark, we consider two different HPC nodes who try to send a message to each other via MPI_Isend. The MPI_Wait is then used to ensure the completion of the communication. We perform local computations while messages are moving. The local computation time is varied to see the effect of the overlapping communication with computation.

We run the microbenchmark for three size of messages:

- Message that has size equal to what our application uses (1.0x Message Size).
- Message that has size 0.1x of what our application uses (0.1x Message Size).
- Message that has size 3x of what our application uses (3.0x Message Size).

Results shown in Figure 1 indicates that if local compute time is large enough, communication can be hidden when asynchronous message progression is activated for Intel MPI. Further observation is as follows.

¹http://hibd.cse.ohio-state.edu/static/media/talks/slide/boothtalk_asyncprogress_1.pdf, slide 19

²<https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/develop/documentation/mpi-developer-guide-linux/top/additional-supported-features/asynchronous-progress-control.html>

- Intel MPI: when the local compute time is small (less than 1 ms for our example), total time depends solely on communication. For larger compute times, communication is completely hidden, resulting in identical values for compute time and total time (perfect overlap).
- OpenMPI: messages are progressed after `MPI_Wait` is called, resulting in non-overlap of communication and computation. Communication time is constant throughout, and total time increases linearly with the local compute time.